

Excerpts from Project Documentation Group 23

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2019-04-08

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0.1 relative performance results

The following tables compare the performance of the AOEU algorithm with a more conventional colouring algorithm, as per the specifications of module 7 - Discrete Structures and Efficient Algorithms. All graph sets tested on were provide by the module.

	GI1	Colouring	AOEU	AOEU - Danger
Correctly Solved	V	V	V	V
Comp time in s	0.0119	0.0364	0.0640	
	GI2	Colouring	AOEU	AOEU - Danger
Correctly Solved	V	V	X	
Comp time in s	0.0245	0.0546	0.0531	
	GI3	Colouring	AOEU	AOEU - Danger
Correctly Solved	V	V	X	
Comp time in s	0.4713	1.1757	0.4744	
	GIAut	Colouring	AOEU	AOEU - Danger
Correctly Solved	V	V	X	
Comp time in s	3.6463	0.1226	0.0721	

0.2 AOEU and graph_to_tree

AOEU uses graph_to_tree, which used to resemble Dijkstra, to turn the graphs into trees, given a start vertex. Two isomorphic graphs, given two isomorphically correspondent start nodes, will also return two isomorphic trees. Given this, AOEU tries to find two isomorphically correspondent vertices to use as start nodes. To limit the problem space, we would only compare nodes with equal degree, and would run the graph_to_tree on both, and check whether or not the resulting trees are isomorphic. Intuitively, failing to find to a vertex with a unique degree in both graphs, we would take all vertices with the least common degree, run graph_to_tree on both of them, and check the equality of the sets.

Figure 1: Tree for Graph 1

The actual graph to tree algorithm, as mentioned before, was based on Dijkstra. There are two important differences: firstly, it does not return a list of distances and backtracking routes, but the tree of routes from the start vertex (it is useful to think of this as a minimal spanning tree over the graph); secondly, the cost function is unorthodox. The value of a given vertex is a list of the degree of all vertices above it in the tree, followed by its own degree; so a vertex with degree 3 that can be reached from the start vertex with degree 1, via a vertex with degree 6, would have the value $[1, 6, 3]$.

The actual cost comparison function consists of two steps. First, if the list for one vertex is shorter than the other, that vertex is chosen. If both values are of equal length, we start comparing the pairs of corresponding list elements from the first value onwards; once an unequal pair is found, the vertex that contained the lower value is chosen. If both values are equal, this poses a number of problems we will go into under section about the false negative issue; at this stage, the one which occurred first is chosen.

To illustrate, the three graphs from the lecture slides would have the trees described in figures ??, ??, and ??

As you can see, the third tree is clearly not isomorphic to the other two, in accordance with the conclusion reached by colour refinement in the lecture.

Note that while the algorithm is structured like Dijkstra, the cost function prioritises shorter paths first, making it practically very similar to breadth first

Figure 2: Tree for Graph 2

Figure 3: Tree for Graph 3

Figure 4: Graph 1

search. In addition, the expansion of a node means adding all of its children to the tree; a node that has been visited is already in the tree. Therefore, if a node in the frontier is in the tree, but does not have its children expanded, that implies a node in the frontier is also in the visited list; when reading the code, it might help to keep this fact in mind.

By itself, this algorithm would have the same complexity as Dijkstra, being $O(E + V \log(V))$. However, the function that finds the best node out of the frontier here has a worst-case complexity of $O(n^2)$, so the actual complexity of the graph to tree algorithm is $O(V^3)$ (see the comments in the code for a more detailed explanation). In the worst case scenario, every vertex will have to be taken as a start vertex, giving the entire algorithm as time complexity of $O(V^4)$, and a spacial complexity of $O(V^2)$, as there is one tree containing all vertices for each vertex. Afterwards, the checking of the set equality would run in $O(n^2)$ (n being the number of elements in the set; the sets are unsorted), and the tree isomorphism function runs in $O(V \log(V))$, so the next step would run in $O(V^3 \log(V))$; the function is still bound by $O(V^4)$.

0.2.1 The false positive issue

There is a specific type of graph substructure that can have differences which are not isomorphic, but will result in isomorphic trees. Take the figures ?? and ??

Clearly, these are not isomorphic. However, given vertex 0 as the start vertex, vertices 1, 2, 3, and 4 would be bound to the same point in the tree and have the same degree; as such, the algorithm would think the two graphs isomorphic.

Figure 5: Graph 2

This problem arises because the problematic edges do not end up in the tree. A solution would be to run the algorithm on any of the other vertices. If one starts at e.g. vertex 1, the difference between the two graphs would be caught. Therefore, to solve the issue, we simply need to compare every vertex of one graph to every vertex in the other graph. This seems incredibly inefficient. but recall that in the worst case scenario, we already generate a tree for every node in graph 2; as such, the total complexity only doubles, and the bound of the complexity does not actually change at all. To preserve the low complexity of graphs which are very different, we still only compare trees generated by start vertices of the same degree.

0.2.2 The false negative issue

Another possible issue are vertices where two parents which have the same value but are not isomorphic, as can be seen in figure ???. Given any start node, e.g. the bottom node with degree 1, the substructure at the top could be bound to either of the nodes with degree three.

In this case, the left tree of figure ??, it has been bound to the left vertex, but one can imagine that in a mirrored graph, which is trivially isomorphic, the substructure would be bound to the right (then left) vertex, resulting in a non-isomorphic tree. Our solution is simply to bind the ambiguous vertex to both parents, duplicating that entire part of the tree. This results in the middle tree of figure ??.

The old function resides in `graphtotree.py`, whereas the new one, with this fix, can be found in `graphtotree2.py`. There are two important differences:

Figure 6: Graph 4

firstly, the `frontier.best` function, which picks the best node out of the frontier, now returns a list instead of a single value; secondly, the correspondence, which maps vertices in the graph to nodes in the tree, now maps a single graph vertex to a list of tree nodes.

Unfortunately, the complexity suffers greatly from this fix. In the worst case scenario, the graph would be a mesh of some sort, and the issue would occur at every node. This would raise the complexity to $O(2^n)$. However, a problematic vertex does not have to be bound to two parents, it could be bound to three, four, or even n parents which form an issue. The more equal parents such a node has, the more duplicates need to be made per node, and the higher the base of the complexity gets; however, the tree would be shallower with the same amount of nodes. We suspect the complexity to be something along the lines of $O(x^n y)$, where $x < n$ and y is the inverse of x . At the very least, we can be sure that the complexity is bound by $O(n^n)$.

0.2.3 The Dangerous Version

To solve the non-polynomiality of the algorithm as described above, a dangerous version of `graph_to_tree` was developed. Instead of branching both ways, it removes the entire problematic substructure from the output tree, as can be seen in the right tree of figure ??

This means that the algorithm is now once again polynomial; however, it does not work for all graphs. Note that this algorithm is not just unsafe, it is

Figure 7: Trees for graph 4. Left: base algorithm. Middle: safe version. Right: Dangerous version

dangerous.

It should be noted that there are currently bugs in the implementation for this algorithm, and there was not enough time to fix them.

0.2.4 Actually Checking the Isomorphism

After turning the graph into a set of trees as described above, we want to actually check for Isomorphism. We do this through a combination of the classical AHU algorithm for Tree isomorphism, and canonisation. Essentially, we “colour” each tree using the AHU algorithm, which eventually returns a single value that is assigned to the root node. We store the values for each root of each tree generated by the AOEU algorithm in a list, which is then sorted. Now, if we want to check if a graph is isomorphic to another graph, all we have to do is construct this sorted list of root nodes and check whether they are the same. If the sorted lists are the same, the graphs are isomorphic. If they are not, they are not isomorphic.

0.2.5 Advantages of AOEU

We can think of two practical advantages of AOEU over other graph isomorphism algorithms.

Firstly, AOEU is very fast on graphs that have vertices of many different degrees, which in practice occur in many practical fields. Especially chemical graphs are very well suited to AOEU, because not only do they often have vertices of many different (and not too high) degrees, but the labels that the vertices already have (i.e. the element) can be put directly into the tree instead of relying on the degree of the vertex alone.

Secondly, the algorithm can not just be used as an isomorphism checker, but also as a canoniser. One could generate the set of trees for a graph, then sort the trees internally, then sort the set of trees, and the resulting bytestring would be the same for every graph isomorphism. If one wants to have a database of graphs, such an algorithm would be incredibly important for lookups. Furthermore, one could use the polynomial time dangerous version of the algorithm to make a canonical version of the graph, and then run a safe graph isomorphism checker to check whether the query graph is different from any matches that are found; this could be a relatively fast way to check whether or not a certain graph is already in a very large database of graphs.

As opposed to the colouring algorithm, AOEU solved most of the bonus instances within the time limit; in fact it solved instance one in about a second, instance 2 in about 0.25 seconds, and instance 5 in about 2 seconds.